

***IPOMOEA HEDERIFOLIA* L.(CONVOLVULACEAE): A NEW RECORD TO THE
FLORA OF HARYANA STATE OF INDIA**

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Abstract: *Ipomoea hederifolia* L. a member of angiospermic family Convolvulaceae has been recognised as a new record to the flora of Haryana state india. New records are the species which were not recorded by previous workers from the same region but present study explores that species. In earlier floristic studies it has been explored from Kerala, Asam, Bihar, Maharasra and Jammu & Kasmir States of India. It is a native of Tropical America but now naturalised in Tropical asia.

Introduction:

Ipomoea hederifolia L. is a weak, slender climber up to 3 m length. Genus *Ipomoea* belongs to family Convolvulaceae. All members of this family are not climbers; some are herbs and sarmentose shrubs. Leaves are alternate, entire or variously lobed, exstipulate, sometimes absent. Flowers are usually bracteate, solitary, panicled or in cymes, actinomorphic or zygomorphic, bisexual. Sepals are 5, free or connate, equal or unequal, sometimes accrescent in fruit. Corolla are 5-lobed, tubular or campanulate, sometimes contorted. Stamens are 4-5, inserted near the base of corolla lobes and alternating with it, anthers are 2-locular, opening lengthwise. Ovary is superior, 2-4-locular, ovules 1-2 in each cell, placentation axile, styles 1-2, stigmas 1-4. Fruit is a capsule or berry, 1-4-seeded.

Methodology:

Extensive surveys of entire area in different seasons (Summer, Rainy, Winter, Spring) were carried out to complete this taxonomic work for 5 years. Three collection surveys were carried out in each season in order to explored entire area randomly during a year. Attempts were made to cover all the area for collection of plants in flowering and/or fruiting stages following standard procedures (Jain & Rao, 1977). Geographical coordinates for the location of plants species were also recorded for each species by using Global positioning system (GPS). The species is collected during the field survey and critically examined under stereo zoom dissecting microscope to record the morphological characters as well as variations available within the species; photographs of this species and field notes were also considered for this purpose. New records are the species which were not recorded by previous workers from the same region but present study explores that species. New records were recorded after comparison of present findings with the previous works in same region (Duthie, 1903-1929; Nair, 1978; Jain *et al.*, 2000). New records are the species which were not recorded by previous workers from the same region but present study explores that species

Figure 1: Google earth satellite image showing exact location of new records along with geocoordinates.

Results and Discussion:

Ipomoea hederifolia L. a member of family Convolvulaceae has been found during the present study as a new record to the flora of Haryana State, India. The species is collected during the field survey and critically examined under stereo zoom dissecting microscope to record the morphological characters as well as variations available within the species; photographs of this species and field notes were also considered for this purpose.

Ipomoea hederifolia Linn., Syst. Nat. (ed. 10.) 2: 925, 1759; *I angulata* Lamk., Tabl. Encycl. 1: 464, 1793; Santapau, Rec. Bot. Surv. Ind. 16 (1); 192, 1953; Maheshw., Fl. Delhi 233; *Quamoclit phoenicea* (Roxb.) Choisy, Mem. Soc. Phys. Geneve 6: 433, 1833; Duthie, Fl. Upp. Gang. Pl. 2: 122; *Ipomoea coccinea* Clarice in Hooker, Fl. Br. Ind. IV: 199 (non Linn.); *Quamoclit coccinea* Cooke, Fl. Pres. Bomb. 2: 261, 1904.

Synonyms: *Ipomoea angularis* Willd., *Ipomoea brevipedicellata* (Hall. fil.) Hall. fil., *Ipomoea coccinea* Rottl., *Ipomoea coccinea* var. *hederifolia* (L.) A.Gray, *Ipomoea acutangula* Ruiz & Pav., *Ipomoea angulata* Lam., *Convolvulus sanguineus* (Vahl) Spreng., *Ipomoea dichotoma* Kunth, *Ipomoea phoenicea* Roxb., *Ipomoea stylosa* Hort. Madr. ex Choisy, *Quamoclit brevipedicellata* Hall. fil., *Quamoclit hederifolia* (L.) G. Don, *Quamoclit russelliiflora* Mart. & Gal., *Quamoclit phoenicea* Wight ex Meisn., *Quamoclit sanguinea* (Vahl) G. Don.

Vernacular name: Lal pungli.

English Name: Red morning-glory, Scarlet creeper, Red Star Glory.

Marathi Name: Lal Pungli.

Malayalam: Suryakanti

Kannada: Haalu Balli

A pretty, twining annual. Leaves 4-8 x 3.5-7 cm, petioled, entire or 3-5-angled, ovate-cordate, acute, glabrous, entire or lobed. Flowers scarlet red, in few-flowered, lax, axillary cymes. Peduncles 5-8 cm long, Calyx lobes 5, 2-4 mm long. Corolla salver-shaped tube to 3.5 cm long, tomato red colour, limb 1.5-2.5 cm. Capsule 5-6 mm, subglobose, 4-celled. Seeds black, pyriform.

Flowering and Fruiting: October-March.

Occurrence and associations: Infrequent, occurs in river side forest.

Habit: Climber.

Parul: 300, Kalesar National Park.

Geocoordinates for new record: 30.374660° N, 77.563035° E

Altitude: 393 m.

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